

Forecast Models for Urban Extreme Temperatures (KATHAMNDU REGION AS A CASE STUDY)

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Abstract: The climatic signature of global warming is both local and global. The forcing by increasing greenhouse gases is global, so there is clearly a global component to the climatic signature. Moreover, the damaging impacts of global warming are manifesting themselves around the world in the form of extreme weather events like storms, tornadoes, floods and droughts, all of which have been escalating in frequency and intensity. Furthermore, it is a well-known fact that there is high degree of uncertainty surrounding projections of basic climate variables, such as temperature and precipitation. However, numerous authors have explored many of these effects individually and have begun exploring the interactions between climate change-induced impacts in different sectors of urban activities. Therefore, it is safe to say that an attempt to conduct a definitive, comprehensive analysis of all the potential impacts of climate change on the urban structure is premature at present. This communication attempts to examine the trends in maximum monthly urban temperature fluctuations. Analysis reveals increasing trends in urban temperature fluctuations showing effect of Kathamndu industrializations. Forecast models also suggest future scenario with respect to occurrence of extreme temperature. The analysis carried out in this work would be useful for urban planners for sustainable future development, economists and environmentalists etc.

Keywords: *Global warming, Temperature fluctuations, Greenhouse gases, Climate, ACF and PACF*

I. Introduction

Global warming (GW) is now an accepted fact that is influencing the lower atmosphere as well as the oceans of the globe [1] and that the climate parameters remain in dynamic equilibrium [2]. In addition, the dynamics of the climate system is chaotic [3-4]. Thus for a better planning, urban planners need to have a clear insight of the situation in future. This requires plausible forecasts of future population and other urban parameters. Fortunately, over the years, researchers have successfully developed sophisticated tools for obtaining better forecasts to support urban planning and management. In recent years, increasing number of studies has appeared dealing with the impact of intense heat on health of urban dwellers [5]. Here, we are not attempting to make a comprehensive assessment of the scientific literature corresponding to climate change. However, to mention some, are the significant correlation between eleven years sun sunspots cycles and ozone layer depletion over arctic region determined by [6-7], the determination of the presence of positive trend in global warming making the quantity of seawater increase due to increasing input from the lakes, underground water, and polar region glaciers and the acceleration in its fluctuations of the GW [8]. Situation in different regions can differ because of different structure, climatic conditions and different conditions of the oceans but the basic facts remain the same. However, the consequences can differ [9]. Urban structures parameters, for example, thermal and radioactive properties of the artificial surfaces modify the climate at both city scale and local scale. The main influence of the cities on microclimate is the heat island caused by radioactive trapping in urban materials. To predict overheating periods within the urban region, this communication attempts to give short- and long-term forecasts of urban extreme temperatures. Long-term forecasts are specially used by urban planners in designing of urban reserve areas and are more importantly, for sustainable urban development. The use of time series provided by modern remote sensing platforms, in particular improves the quality of derived ecological indicators. These indicators can be generated on a global scale from optical/thermal remote sensing data. The quality of ecological indicators, especially in complex terrain, is determined by thorough pre- and postprocessing of the data in order to minimize artifacts in the resulting maps. The MODIS sensor is currently the optimal match between temporal and spatial resolution and is an excellent data source for both local and global change research. The paper is organized as follows.

Section 2 reviews ARIMA modeling theory briefly.

In Section 3, urban monthly maximum temperature fluctuations are modeled. Section 4 gives a comparison of trends of 47 years mean monthly maximum temperature fluctuations of the mega city of Kathmandu with Mahendranagar, a much smaller city. Finally, Section 5 concludes this work.

II. Time Series Analysis

In general, the primary goals of conducting a time series analysis are: a. Characterizing the nature of the phenomenon represented by the sequence of observations, and b. Forecasting or predicting future values of the time series variable. The focus of this study is on the forecasting capabilities of the models. Hydrologic processes usually exhibit time dependence,

known as autocorrelation, between a given observation at some time t denoted by z_t and some previous observations, z_{t-1} , z_{t-2} etc. and with those occurring at the same time during the previous season(s), denoted by z_{t-s} . The autoregressive, integrated, moving-average (ARIMA) model developed by Box and Jenkins (1976), is denoted as ARIMA $(p, d, q) \times (P, D, Q)_s$, where p = order of the non-seasonal autoregressive process,

d = number of consecutive differencing,

q = order of the non-seasonal moving average process,

P = order of the seasonal autoregressive process,

D = number of seasonal differencing,

Q = order of the seasonal moving average process, and

s = the span of the seasonality. Box (1994), developed a systematic class of models called autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models to handle time-correlated modeling and forecasting [10-11]. The ARIMA methodology has gained enormous popularity

in many areas, and research practice confirms its power and flexibility, especially when patterns of the data were unclear and individual observations involved considerable error [12]. In this study, their application to seasonal data is particularly important. The Box Jenkins approach consists of extracting the predictable movements from the observed data. It primarily makes use of three linear filters known as the autoregressive, the integration and the moving average filter. The objective in applying these filters is to end up with a white noise process which is unpredictable. Once this is done successfully, we have a model that has properties similar to the process itself. This model can then provide a basis for accurate and reliable forecasts. By combining differencing, autoregressive and moving-average representations in one model, Box and Jenkins were able to propose a parsimonious class of models called the ARIMA models [13]. They are applied in some cases where data show evidence of non-stationarity, where an initial differencing step (corresponding to the "integrated" part of the model) can be applied to remove the non-stationarity. The Box - Jenkins procedure has been found useful by many researchers but extremely complex, requiring quite a bit of experience to use effectively. Next, we apply this modeling technique to the Arabian Sea monthly averaged seawater temperature data to obtain reliable forecast models [14].

III. Time Series Models for Maximum Temperature Fluctuations

This section reports the ARIMA forecast models using mean monthly maximum temperatures (1961-2007) of Kathmandu region. The forecasts are made for 2008-2012. Computer software MINITAB version 14 was used for the estimation of statistically significant model parameters. Appropriated models were selected for which values of modified Box-Pierce Q statistic and Auto Integrated Correlation

$AIC = \sigma^2 k + (\eta + 2k) / \eta$ showed minimum. In AIC, $\sigma^2 k = (RSS) / \eta$ and k is the number of parameters in the model. The value of k yielding the minimum AIC specifies the best model [21]. On the basis of Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) structure it is possible to create parametric mathematical models that are able to simulate a data generating process and extrapolate the time series to the future periods.

IV. Comparison of Kathmandu Urban Extreme Temperatures with Mahendranagar Urban Extreme Temperatures:

To show that global warming is affecting the mega cities more than the smaller cities, we compare the extreme temperatures of the coastal mega city of Kathmandu and the comparatively smaller city of Mahendranagar. The estimated population (2009) are between 2 and 3 million. Located in the middle of Nepal. The Kathmandu valley has a mild climate most of the year. The average maximum daytime temperature in January is 64.4°F (18°C), rising to an

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average maximum of around 84.2°F (29°C) in July. There is a rainy monsoon season between June and August, while May and June can be very hot and humid. In spring (March to April) and autumn (October to November) the temperatures are

pleasant with occasional short bursts of rain, while November to February is dry, but can be very cold, especially at night. Mean annual precipitation is 56.18 inches (1427mm). Kathmandu valley is bowl-shaped. Its central lower part stands at 1,425 metres (4,675 ft) above sea level. Kathmandu valley is surrounded by four mountain ranges: Shivapuri hills (at an elevation of 2,732 metres or 8,963 feet), Phulchowki (2,695 metres or 8,842 feet), Nagarjun (2,095 metres or 6,873 feet) and Chandragiri (2,551 metres or 8,369 feet). The major river flowing through the Kathmandu Valley is the Bagmati.

V. Conclusion

Urban mean monthly maximum temperature data sets have been examined to see the rate of increase in six decades due to urban activities. It has been observed that almost every month has increasing trend except for the month of July, which has, more or less, steady trend. It has also been observed that the second summer season in Kathmandu region has higher trend values as compared to the first summer season. This reflects the fact that the urban activities in any mega-city greatly affect the local temperature fluctuations. This situation in Mhendranagar also reflects this fact as there is no appreciable change in the trends of local extreme temperature. Forecast models of local temperature variations would be useful for urban planners and for environmental control strategies. It is imperative to find modern methods of adaptation to the climate impacts focusing on urban and rural categories. The working with seasonal temperature variations, sea surface temperature fluctuations and the role of urban population would be important to clarify the linkage among these urban parameters. This could also enhance the understanding of daily or weekly temperature variability. Further studies are needed to be undertaken to explore the sensitivity of these results with respect to other parameters. For this purpose, the extreme value theory seems more promising.

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